

RISIS

RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE FOR SCIENCE
AND INNOVATION POLICY STUDIES

VICO *Basic Tutorial*

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1 Introduction

The VICO database contains geographical, industry and accounting information on 17,854 companies founded starting from 1/1/1988, which have received at least one venture capital or angel investment starting from 1/1/1998 up to 31/12/2014, operating in 7 European countries (Belgium, Finland, France, Germany, Italy, Spain, and the United Kingdom) and Israel. Companies and investors have been involved in 28,023 investment deals. Moreover, it provides basic information on 6,839 distinct investors, of which 5,172 venture capitalists (VCs) and 1,551 business angels (BAs) (plus a small percentage of other investors, e.g. crowdfunding, private equity...). Companies and investors have been involved in 28,023 investment deals, for a total of 52,629 observations (as one or more investors can be involved in each single investment round).

The database is operated and maintained by Politecnico di Milano, Department of Management, Economics and Industrial Engineering, located in Via Lambruschini 4/b, Milano, 20156, Italy. It is currently available in the .dta format (Stata). It is structured in two main Tables: the Investment Table, which contains information at the deal level (unit of analysis: company-investor-round number), and the Accounting Table, which contains information on accounting variables (unit of analysis: company-year).

2 Basic User Guide

2.1 Opening the file

VICO DB is available in STATA format. The following example uses STATA 14 to illustrate the basic operations that can be run using Cheetah database

VICO files can be opened in Stata with the command *use*, specifying the file path. When using Stata, the commands can be saved in a Do-file, as shown in Figure 1. To view and edit data, Data editor can be accessed through the command *browse*, or by clicking the Data Editor icon in the manual menu as shown in Figure 2, or by selecting Data > Data Editor > Data Editor (Browse) from the menu as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 1: use and browse commands

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The screenshot shows the Stata software interface. The top menu bar includes 'Open', 'Save', 'Print', 'Log', 'Viewer', 'Graph', 'File Editor', 'Data Editor', and 'Data Browser'. The 'Data Editor' menu item is circled in blue. The main window is divided into three panes: 'Review' (Command window), 'Results', and 'Variables'. The 'Review' pane shows the command `use "/Users/Benedetta/Dropbox (DIG)/VIC0.dta"`. The 'Results' pane displays the Stata startup screen, including the Stata logo, version 15.1, and copyright information. The 'Variables' pane lists the variables in the dataset, with their names and labels.

Name	Label
CompanyID	CompanyID
RoundNumber	RoundNumber
InvestmentDate	InvestmentDate
InvestmentYear	InvestmentYear
CompanyName	CompanyName_Final...
CompanyName_with_legal_form	
CompanyID_Orbis	CompanyID_Orbis
CompanyID_Orbis_2018	New ID
CompanyName_Orbis	
CompanyNACERev2Coremainsec	
CompanyNACERev2mainsec	
CompanyNACERev2Corecode	
CompanyNACERev2Corecodes	
CompanyNACERev2codes	
CompanyNACERev2descriptions	
CompanyFoundedYear	CompanyFoundedYear
FirstInvestmentReceivedYear	FirstInvestmentRecei...
FirstInvestmentReceivedDate	FirstInvestmentRecei...
CompanyNation	
CompanyCity	
CompanyAddress	

Figure 2: Stata menu

The screenshot shows the Stata Data Editor interface. The top menu bar includes 'Filter', 'Variables', 'Properties', and 'Snapshots'. The 'Edit' menu item is circled in blue. The main window is divided into three panes: 'Data Editor (Browse)', 'Variables', and 'Properties'. The 'Data Editor' pane shows a table of data with columns for CompanyID, RoundNumber, InvestmentDate, and InvestmentYear. The 'Variables' pane lists the variables in the dataset, with their names and labels. The 'Properties' pane shows the properties of the selected variable, CompanyID.

CompanyID	RoundNumber	InvestmentDate	InvestmentYear
VIC04948	1	3/13/2014	2014
VIC013642	1	10/18/2012	2012
VIC07745	1	12/12/2011	2011
VIC06632	2	8/13/2012	2012
VIC08502	1	6/1/2013	2013
VIC09547	2	2/16/2015	2015
VIC04664	1	10/27/2014	2014
VIC04442	1	7/3/2012	2012
VIC01381	4	9/20/2002	2002
VIC04400	1	5/3/2012	2012
VIC04510	1	9/18/2014	2014
VIC017140	5	3/14/2008	2008
VIC05173	1	4/3/2006	2006
VIC03711	1	9/30/2005	2005
VIC08597	2	5/3/2011	2011
VIC05877	1	5/26/2014	2014
VIC06628	1	5/12/2009	2009
VIC018537	2	4/17/2014	2014
VIC0482	1	10/27/2014	2014
VIC01961	1	2/13/2003	2003
VIC019282	1	3/1/2000	2000
VIC09215	1	3/20/2014	2014
VIC04140	2	12/5/2001	2001
VIC02087	8	5/31/2008	2008
VIC05895	1	11/16/2008	2008
VIC01308	2	9/8/2003	2003
VIC04855	1	7/12/2013	2013
VIC07230	1	12/31/2002	2002
VIC07556	1	10/22/2013	2013

Figure 3: Data Editor

After opening the Cheetah database with STATA, we can see on the right side a panel (Figure 2 and Figure 3) with a summary of the variables available in the database. In particular, the variable have a Name, which can be used to refer to them in the command line, and a Label containing a short human-readable description of the variable.

By clicking with the left mouse button on a variable, that variable will be selected, and additional information will be shown in the Properties panel. Additional information include the type of the variable (in this case, a string) and the format. Moreover, in the Data subpanel, additional information for the whole dataset is available, like the total number of variables, the number of observations, and the dimension of the database in memory.

To actual edit the variables in the DB, we have to open the Data Editor window in the Edit mode by clicking on Edit on the up-right corner (see Figure 3).

2.2 Descriptive statistics

To gain insights into the structure of data, data can be summarized typing *summarize* (or just *sum*) in the command window. The result is a table containing summary statistics about all the variables in the dataset, as shown in Figure 5. Alternatively, it is possible to personalize the descriptive statistics obtained, using the command *tabstat* and specifying the variables names and the list of the specific statistics needed.

```
3 summarize
4 tabstat RoundNumber InvestmentDate InvestmentYear, statistics(count mean sd median p25 p75 range variance skewness kurtosis) col(stat) varwidth(32)
```

Figure 4: descriptive statistics command

. summarize

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
CompanyID	0				
RoundNumber	52,629	1.922438	1.640771	1	19
Investment~e	52,629	17347.52	1815.474	13880	20178
Investment~r	52,629	2006.993	4.970051	1998	2015
CompanyName	0				

Figure 5: summarize output

```
. tabstat RoundNumber InvestmentDate InvestmentYear, statistics(count mean sd median p25 p75 range variance s  
> kewness kurtosis) col(stat) varwidth(32)
```

variable	N	mean	sd	p50	p25	p75	range
RoundNumber	52629	1.922438	1.640771	1	1	2	18
InvestmentDate	52629	17347.52	1815.474	17393	15748	19036	6298
InvestmentYear	52629	2006.993	4.970051	2007	2003	2012	17

variable	variance	skewness	kurtosis
RoundNumber	2.69213	2.968409	15.22651
InvestmentDate	3295944	-.0795179	1.683943
InvestmentYear	24.7014	-.071227	1.687043

Figure 6: *tabstat* output

2.3 Sectoral, geographical and temporal distributions of the companies

From now on, to illustrate the next basic commands, we refer to the Investment Table, containing data at the level of single investment deals. To see how many companies are included into the VICO database, we have to move to the level of single firms (obtaining one line for each company). In order to do that, the following code can be executed:

```
6 sort CompanyID
7 quietly by CompanyID: gen dup = cond(_N==1,0,_n)
8 drop if dup > 1
9 drop dup
```

Figure 7: obtaining one line for each company

To see how companies are distributed in terms of industry, the variable referring to the NACE Rev. 2 classification (CompanyNACERev2Coremainsec) can be used. With the command *tabulate*, or *tab*, followed by the variable of interest, it is possible to obtain a two-way table of frequency counts, displayed in Table 1.

The same can be done for geographical distribution, using *tab* followed by the variable CompanyNation. The output is shown in Table 2.

```
5 tabulate CompanyNACERev2Coremainsec
6 tabulate CompanyNation
7
```

Figure 8: *tabulate* command

NACE Rev. 2 Main Section	N. Companies	Percent
A - Agriculture, forestry and fishing	18	0.14
B - Mining and quarrying	40	0.3
C - Manufacturing	2,020	15.36
D - Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply	95	0.72
E - Water supply; sewerage, waste management	43	0.33
F - Construction	192	1.46
G - Wholesale and retail trade; repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles	1,173	8.92
H - Transportation and storage	123	0.94
I - Accommodation and food service activities	131	1
J - Information and communication	4,620	35.14
K - Financial and insurance activities	605	4.6
L - Real estate activities	102	0.78
M - Professional, scientific and technical activities	2,524	19.2
N - Administrative and support services activities	870	6.62
O - Public administration and defence; compulsory social security	3	0.02
P - Education	66	0.5
Q - Human health and social work activities	196	1.49
R - Arts, entertainment and recreation	131	1
S - Other service activities	193	1.47
T - Activities of households as employers; undifferentiated goods and services-producing activities of households for own use	3	0.02
Total	13,148	100.00

Table 1: sectoral distribution

Country	N. Companies	Percent
Belgium	557	3.12
Finland	1,042	5.84
France	3,868	21.66
Germany	3,093	17.32
Israel	1,240	6.95
Italy	738	4.13
Spain	1,454	8.14
United Kingdom	5,862	32.83
Total	17,854	100

Table 2: geographical distribution

To count companies belonging to a specific sector, or a specific country, the command *count if* can be used.

Figure 9: *count if* command

```
count if CompanyNation == "United Kingdom"
count if CompanyNACERev2Coremainsec == "J - Information and communication"
```

```
. count if CompanyNation == "United Kingdom"
5,862

. count if CompanyNACERev2Coremainsec == "J - Information and communication"
4,620
```

Figure 10: *count if* output

To study firms distribution in terms of foundation year, an additional step must be performed to group the companies into classes. For this purpose, it is possible to create a new variable, through the command *generate*, or *gen*, called *foundation_year_class*, and assign to that variable different values according to when the company has been founded (variable *CompanyFoundedYear*). At this point, it is possible to use the *tabulate* command to see the distribution table. The code is displayed in Figure 11, and the output in Table 3.

```
17 gen foundation_year_class = "before 1990" if CompanyFoundedYear < 1990
18 replace foundation_year_class = "1990<=y<1995" if (CompanyFoundedYear < 1995 & CompanyFoundedYear>= 1990)
19 replace foundation_year_class = "1995<=y<2000" if (CompanyFoundedYear < 2000 & CompanyFoundedYear>= 1995)
20 replace foundation_year_class = "2000<=y<2005" if (CompanyFoundedYear < 2005 & CompanyFoundedYear>= 2000)
21 replace foundation_year_class = "2005<=y<2010" if (CompanyFoundedYear < 2010 & CompanyFoundedYear>= 2005)
22 replace foundation_year_class = "2010<=y<2015" if (CompanyFoundedYear < 2015 & CompanyFoundedYear>= 2010)
23 tabulate foundation_year_class
```

Figure 11: creation of new variable "foundation_year_class"

Foundation year	N. Companies	Percent
before 1990	463	3.32
1990 \leq y<1995	974	6.99
1995 \leq y<2000	2,886	20.71
2000 \leq y<2005	3,735	26.81
2005 \leq y<2010	3,462	24.85
2010 \leq y<2015	2,412	17.31
Total	13,932	100.00

Table 3:

by foundation year

distribution

A similar process can be followed to investigate firms distribution according to the year in which they received their first investment. The code is shown in Figure 12, and the output in Table 4.

```
25 gen first_inv_year_class = "before 2000" if FirstInvestmentReceivedYear < 2000
26 replace first_inv_year_class = "2000<=y<2005" if (FirstInvestmentReceivedYear < 2005 & FirstInvestmentReceivedYear>= 2000)
27 replace first_inv_year_class = "2005<=y<2010" if (FirstInvestmentReceivedYear < 2010 & FirstInvestmentReceivedYear>= 2005)
28 replace first_inv_year_class = "2010<=y<2015" if (FirstInvestmentReceivedYear < 2015 & FirstInvestmentReceivedYear>= 2010)
29 tabulate first_inv_year_class
```

First Investment Year	N. Companies	Percent
before 2000	1,236	6.92
2000≤y<2005	5,796	32.46
2005≤y<2010	4,722	26.45
2010≤y≤2015	6,100	34.17
Total	17,854	100.00

Table 4: distribution by first investment year

2.4 Bar charts

To obtain visual representation of the variables previously described, histograms can be built. The command to use for this function in Stata is `catplot`.

```

31 catplot CompanyNation
32 catplot foundation_year_class
33 catplot first_inv_year_class

```

Figure 13: `catplot` command

Figure 14: CompanyNation bar chart

Figure 15: foundation_year_class bar chart

Figure 16: first_inv_year bar chart